

New way to obtain less scattered material-relevant threshold ΔK_{th} with crack closure influences quantified

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Abstract

The article presents a new methodology to quantify constituents of applied ΔK corresponding to influences of the traditionally identified crack closure mechanisms occurring during fatigue crack propagation in steels. The values are obtained from the measured crack growth rates, which is different from other methods such as crack closure measurement or modelling. The advantage is that the true observed effect in different materials can be obtained, independently of any presumptions or limitations of the theoretical models. The two near-threshold components roughness-induced crack closure and oxide-induced crack closure (OICC) were separated using data from dry air and humid air. It is emphasized that the threshold ΔK_{th} measured in standard laboratory conditions using the load shedding method is affected and non-conservative (typically between $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ and $8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ at $R = 0.1$). It is suggested that ΔK_{th} as a material parameter for steels should be measured in dry air (typically between $4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ and $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ at $R = 0.1$). In this way it is less scattered, conservative, predictable and more relevant as a material parameter. The OICC component representing the surplus of the ΔK_{th} value in humid air is responsible for the typical large scatter obtained by different authors and for its dependencies on various testing conditions. The OICC effect was observed in both corroding and corrosion-resistant steels. The work contributes to understanding of the influences, which will improve the use of ΔK_{th} in residual fatigue life estimations and which will ensure avoiding of non-conservative scenarios within the testing-simulation-operation scheme.

Key words

fatigue crack growth threshold, crack closure, load shedding, air humidity, steels

1 Introduction

1.1 Fatigue crack growth threshold

The fatigue crack growth threshold, ΔK_{th} , defines the stress-intensity-factor range below which a long fatigue crack does not propagate. It is therefore a key parameter for residual fatigue life (RFL) estimation of cyclically loaded engineering components [1,2], especially when safety is the critical factor during long-term operation. Besides distinguishing between growing and non-growing cracks, the threshold determines which loading cycles may be treated as damaging or non-damaging [3,4]. Although most fatigue crack growth studies focus on the Paris regime, the near-threshold regime still involves unresolved conceptual and methodological problems [2,5,6]. This is critical because even small variations in ΔK_{th} can cause large differences in predicted RFL. Engineering components designed for long service lives are mostly loaded by operational cycles occurring below or only slightly above the threshold [1,3]. Consequently, reliable RFL predictions require precise near-threshold fatigue crack growth data. Threshold determination is an experimentally demanding procedure, requiring long tests and dealing with numerous influences of the testing conditions on the measured values, whose quantitative roles are not yet

1 fully resolved [7-9]. A single threshold measurement cannot describe the possible scatter band and may
2 therefore lead to non-conservative assessments. This uncertainty is also relevant for component testing,
3 since ΔK_{th} is used to decide which loading amplitudes may be omitted from the spectrum [9].

4 Recent studies [7,10,11] documented the interest in the threshold topic by different research groups
5 and confirmed that it is still a highly up-to-date research field. The conclusions of a dedicated workshop
6 summarized in [2] pointed out that the standard threshold measurement methods may produce large
7 scatter and, in some cases, non-conservative values. This scatter is strongly related to the crack tip
8 shielding mechanisms, from which the plasticity-induced crack closure (PICC), roughness-induced crack
9 closure (RICC), and oxide-induced crack closure (OICC) are the most commonly studied constituents
10 [1,12-14]. However, no generally accepted quantitative methodology is available for separating these
11 components in a form suitable for experimental evaluation or RFL simulation. Developing such a
12 methodology is therefore the central motivation of the present work.

13 The measured ΔK_{th} combines intrinsic crack growth resistance with extrinsic shielding effects. The
14 intrinsic (effective) threshold $\Delta K_{th,eff}$ describes the true material resistance to crack advance. Unlike the
15 commonly assumed link with conventional strength parameters, such as yield stress or ultimate tensile
16 strength, $\Delta K_{th,eff}$ depends only on the Young's modulus and the Burgers vector length [15-19]. It is
17 surprisingly well predictable in most metals, which is in contrast to the large scatter of measured ΔK_{th}
18 values under various stress ratios. Therefore, it is the crack closure effect what dominates the applied
19 threshold values and what largely controls its sensitivity to testing conditions [1,2]. Accurate
20 characterization of these influences is thus essential for improving RFL predictions. In the near-threshold
21 regime, crack opening displacements are too small, which complicates both experimental and numerical
22 studies of the phenomena. This is why the present work relies on the analysis of the fatigue crack growth
23 rate data rather than modelling at microscale.

24 **1.2 Challenges in crack closure determination**

25 Although crack closure has been studied for decades, a reliable quantitative description of its
26 individual components is still lacking. Common approaches to the load-ratio effect such as the NASGRO
27 method [20,21] and crack closure studies supported by modelling, e.g. [22] consider only the PICC
28 mechanism even though RICC and OICC may be equally important near threshold. In steels, OICC can
29 form a significant part of ΔK_{th} and may depend strongly on factors such as air humidity and loading
30 frequency [5,23]. These parameters often vary between laboratories and service conditions but are rarely
31 controlled systematically. Threshold measurement is also affected by the fact that the test itself imposes
32 an artificial loading history. As shown by Newman [24], standard load-shedding procedures such as that
33 of ASTM E647 [25] may produce closure-affected non-conservative thresholds.

34 Alternative procedures such as cyclic compression precracking were introduced to reduce the closure
35 effects and obtain more conservative values [26,27]. The precrack produced by cyclic compression-
36 compression loading ensures reduction of the PICC overload effect during load reduction, which in turn
37 also reduces the OICC effect on threshold. Another possibility is to apply the constant- K_{max} methods
38 [2,28,29]. Some argue that high-R closure can also be present when applying these strategies [30].

39 The present work emphasizes that OICC introduces significant loading-history effects in near-
40 threshold testing of steels. If unsuitable procedures are used for materials susceptible to oxide debris
41 formation, the measured threshold may be artificially high, leading to non-conservative predictions of
42 RFLs. The methodology developed here aims to reduce this risk by separating the individual crack
43 closure contributions in a quantitative and experimentally easily applicable way.

1 A reliable description of PICC is necessary before RICC and OICC can be evaluated quantitatively. It
2 was reported that the current PICC models have sometimes limited ability to consistently reproduce the
3 load-ratio effects across different materials [31]. A major limitation is that the models often rely only on
4 the monotonic material properties, despite PICC is also affected by reversed plasticity. The residual
5 crack-wake deformation depends on the tensile plastic stretch during loading as well as on the
6 compressive rebound during unloading [32]. Material microstructural aspects such as sub-grain domains
7 or microfracture of brittle phases also influence the load ratio effect [31]. The common models
8 considering only monotonic properties provide nearly constant PICC values for different materials, while
9 the differences should be much larger to match the observed data in these materials. Sophisticated finite
10 element models may capture cyclic material behaviour, however the crack advance and crack closure
11 depends on many adjustable parameters of the simulation and require experimental verification.
12 Moreover, this method is computationally inefficient for practical RFL applications where millions of
13 cycles should be modelled. In the present approach, these issues are avoided and no numerically modelled
14 PICC values are imposed on the measured FCG rate data. Instead, the actual load-ratio effects are derived
15 directly from the FCG rate data and used to determine PICC phenomenologically.

16 Strip-yield models [33,34] have been widely used for estimating of PICC, which was successful
17 especially for variable amplitude loading. The predictions can be adapted to experimental results by
18 variation of the constraint factor α . It was suggested that a different parameter can be used instead of α to
19 reproduce large differences between materials, which kept the original meaning of α of out-of-plane
20 constraint. The constraint factor in compression β was unused or kept equal to 1. It was suggested to use it
21 to change the ratio of the sizes of monotonic and cyclic plastic zones to fit different material behaviour
22 [31]. In the present work, the crack closure parameter $f = K_{cl}/K_{max}$ was determined from the
23 experimentally observed FCG rate data rather than from modelling. These values, however, can be used
24 to find the corresponding β parameter for strip yield simulations.

25 **1.3 Oxide-induced crack closure and its significance**

26 Oxide-induced crack closure has been known for a long time [35,36] but a practical quantitative
27 description has been missing. Recent studies revealed that thresholds in steels decrease significantly in
28 dry air because oxide debris formation on fracture surfaces is suppressed. [13,23]. OICC develops when
29 oxide and metallic debris is produced and accumulated in the crack wake after repeated fracture-surface
30 contact. This requires the presence of other closure mechanism such as PICC or RICC and a very slow
31 crack growth, typically below about 10^{-6} mm/cycle. In the near-threshold regime, the debris layer can be
32 comparable to the crack opening displacement, which contributes to crack closure substantially. OICC
33 may therefore represent a major part of the applied threshold. At high load ratios, where fracture-surface
34 contact is absent, oxide debris is not generated even at very low crack growth rates. Significant air
35 humidity effect on OICC was reported [13,23] as well as a strong frequency effect on OICC [5]. Low-
36 frequency tests may suppress OICC but they are often impractically long, whereas high-frequency tests
37 may generate excessive oxide debris in comparison to operation and produce non-conservative thresholds.
38 The present work addresses this problem by proposing a procedure that reduces the OICC contribution
39 while maintaining experimentally feasible testing conditions. It also verifies this effect in several more
40 steels and it applies the new methodology of quantification of ΔK_{th} constituents.

1.4 Purpose and aims

A meaningful interpretation of ΔK_{th} requires distinguishing between intrinsic crack growth resistance and extrinsic shielding effects. Further decomposition of the extrinsic contribution into PICC, RICC, and OICC is necessary to determine which parts of the measured threshold represent material behaviour and which parts reflect test conditions, loading history or environment. The aim of the present work is to develop an experimentally applicable methodology for quantifying the mechanistic constituents of ΔK_{th} and to identify the dominant sources of experimental scatter. Thus, it is intended to restore the practical meaning of ΔK_{th} as a material parameter usable in simulations and to avoid non-conservative scenarios of threshold measurement and its application to RFL prediction.

2 New methodology of crack growth rate data processing to separate crack closure mechanisms and to find the material-relevant threshold ΔK_{th}

A new methodology is presented with the purpose of avoiding the problems related to uncertainties of crack closure determination, especially in the near-threshold regime. Apart from the improvement of the accuracy of RFL estimations, the methodology aims to provide better understanding of mechanisms, identification of relevant material properties and other influencing factors.

2.1 Acquisition of crack growth rate data

The procedures of crack growth rate data determination according to standards are often used, e.g. ASTM E647 [25] or ISO 12108 [37]. Several da/dN vs. ΔK data sets should be obtained for various load ratios R in order to have sufficient basis for RFL determination.

The NASGRO equation [20,21] fits the experimental crack growth rate data with a pre-defined crack closure parameter f , which has two disadvantages. First, only the plasticity-induced crack closure mechanism is considered, which results in inaccurate ideas about crack closure in the near-threshold regime. Second, very similar f values are predicted for all materials, which is inconvenient for studying of different material properties. For example, it was reported that for a 3D-printed 304L steel, the f parameter failed to describe the dependence of crack growth rates on the load ratio [31]. In the present study, it is suggested that the f values are determined directly from the crack growth rates, which characterizes the material accurately. It is computed based on the crack growth rates measured at two different load ratios, typically $R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.8$. In the presented analysis, it is sufficient to work with only these two load ratios. For more complex studies, where f should be expressed for any desired R , the use of the f values predicted by NASGRO is currently the only practical and efficient way to do it. The discrepancies between the real material behaviour and the predicted f can be overcome by determining the f using the strip-yield model simulations with an additional variable, as suggested in [31].

In the first step of the described methodology, the following three da/dN vs. ΔK data measurements were done: (i) at $R = 0.1$ in air with normal relative humidity at room temperature, (ii) at $R = 0.1$ in air with relative humidity less than 10% at room temperature (absolute humidity less than 2 g/m^3) and (iii) at $R = 0.8$, where air humidity does not matter, however, it is easier to conduct the test in normal (humid) air. The data including the threshold were obtained in this work using the standard ASTM load shedding method, see Section 3.2 for details. After that, the data were fitted using a special procedure described in the next section.

2.2 Evaluation of the plasticity-induced crack closure effect

2.2.1 Modified fitting procedure

The present approach is based on the idea that it is not purposeful to search for the f parameter by means of numerical simulations or compliance change measurement techniques. Reliability of the results of these approaches is questionable [38,39], there are too many influences and the predicted values need to be verified experimentally anyway. Here, instead, the true experimentally observed load ratio effect is extracted from the crack growth rate data and the f parameter is evaluated accordingly. It expresses the load ratio effect directly as the desired value, regardless of the mechanisms involved or their complexity. This method is applied to the Paris regime data to avoid additional crack closure mechanisms that are active near threshold.

The NASGRO Equation (1) was used in order to ensure compatibility of the approach with the most commonly used methodologies for RFL estimation.

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left[\left(\frac{1-f}{1-R} \right) \Delta K \right]^n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta K_{th}}{\Delta K} \right)^p \quad (1)$$

Here, a is the crack length, N is the number of applied loading cycles, C , n , p and ΔK_{th} are fitting parameters, $f = K_c/K_{max}$ is the crack closure parameter (note that only PICC is included in f), $R = K_{min}/K_{max}$ is the load ratio and ΔK is the applied stress intensity factor range. The term associated with the final fracture in the original NASGRO equation is omitted in this work, since it corresponds to insignificant number of loading cycles and since the loading is usually associated with large-scale yielding, making the K parameter invalid.

In the newly proposed procedure, the first step is that the three described experimentally obtained FCG rate curves are fitted separately using a simplified form of the equation, where ΔK_{eff} is replaced by ΔK . In this way, the term containing f and R is removed, which allows obtaining of two different C coefficients, one for the high load ratio, typically $R = 0.8$, which is denoted as C_{eff} , and one for the low load ratio, $R = 0.1$ in this work, which is denoted $C_{R=0.1}$.

$$\left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)_{R=0.8} = C_{eff} (\Delta K)^n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta K_{eff,th}}{\Delta K} \right)^p \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)_{R=0.1} = C_{R=0.1} (\Delta K)^n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta K_{th}}{\Delta K} \right)^p \quad (3)$$

The coefficient $C_{R=0.1}$ is kept equal for the humid air data and for the dry air data. The threshold values are fitted as different for all three curves, while the exponents n and p are kept equal for all three curves.

2.2.2 Finding of f

The values given by Eq. (2) (high R) should be shifted using the f parameter to obtain the values given by Eq. (3) (low R), thus expressing the PICC effect in the Paris regime. This shift corresponds to the parallel linear parts of the curves in the log-log scale. Thus, the equations can be written without the threshold term, giving Eqs. (2a) and (3a) that enable the mathematical expression of f .

$$\left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)_{R=0.8} = C_{eff} (\Delta K)^n \quad (2a)$$

$$\left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)_{R=0.1} = C_{R=0.1} (\Delta K)^n \quad (3a)$$

Inclusion of the parameter f in Eq. (2a) in the same form as in the NASGRO Eq. (1) must result in the FCG rates equal to those described by Eq. (3a), leading to Eq. (4)

$$\left(\frac{da}{dN}\right)_{R=0.1} = C_{\text{eff}} \left(\Delta K \left(\frac{1-f}{1-R} \right) \right)^n = C_{R=0.1} (\Delta K)^n \quad (4)$$

From here, the relationship between C_{eff} and $C_{R=0.1}$ can be obtained for every $\Delta K \neq 0$:

$$C_{R=0.1} = C_{\text{eff}} \left(\frac{1-f}{1-R} \right)^n \quad (5)$$

Then, the searched f value can be derived as:

$$f = 1 - (1 - R) \left(\frac{C_{R=0.1}}{C_{\text{eff}}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (6)$$

This value represents the PICC effect for the given material along the whole FCG rate curve, which will be used in the further analysis dealing with additional closure components near threshold.

2.2.3 Clarification of the quantitative expression of the PICC effect

In order to correctly describe the PICC effect quantitatively in the further analysis, a certain distinction has to be introduced first. The value of PICC that can be expressed by the parameter f is equal to $K_{\text{PICC}} = f \cdot K_{\text{max}}$. The part of this value lying inside the applied range ΔK should be separated from the part lying below K_{min} , since anything lying outside the range $\Delta K = K_{\text{max}} - K_{\text{min}}$ is non-existent and does not take part on the process. The first part is denoted here as ΔK_{PICC} , which corresponds to the real PICC process occurring within the loading range ΔK . The second part is equal to K_{min} or in the case of negative load ratios R it is equal to 0. The part of PICC lying inside ΔK is then:

$$\Delta K_{\text{PICC}} = \begin{cases} f K_{\text{max}} - K_{\text{min}} & \dots \dots \dots \text{ for } 0 \leq R < 1 \\ f K_{\text{max}} & \dots \dots \dots \text{ for } R < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Considering $K_{\text{max}} = \Delta K / (1 - R)$, the expression takes this form:

$$\Delta K_{\text{PICC}} = \Delta K \left(\frac{f - R^+}{1 - R} \right), \quad (8)$$

where $R^+ = R$ for $0 \leq R < 1$ and $R^+ = 0$ for $R < 0$. This is the component of PICC active within the applied ΔK , which is important for the identification of the other closure components described in the following sections.

2.3 Evaluation of the roughness-induced crack closure component

In the present methodology, the RICC component is evaluated as the remaining part of ΔK that is not covered by the sum of ΔK_{eff} and ΔK_{PICC} . Based on the data measured in dry air, where OICC is neglected, the composition of ΔK is as follows:

$$\Delta K = \Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K_{\text{PICC}} + \Delta K_{\text{RICC}} \quad (9)$$

Using Eq. (8) for ΔK_{PICC} , the term ΔK_{RICC} can be derived from Eq. (9) to obtain:

$$\Delta K_{\text{RICC}} = \Delta K - \Delta K_{\text{PICC}} - \Delta K_{\text{eff}} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta K_{\text{RICC}} = \Delta K \left[1 - \left(\frac{f-R^+}{1-R} \right) \right] - \Delta K_{\text{eff}} . \quad (11)$$

3 This is a different approach from any kind of RICC modelling or fracture surface roughness
 4 observation. Such obtained value could be generally called a "near-threshold closure surplus" that adds to
 5 PICC. It is a phenomenological value that does not say anything about the mechanism actually causing it.
 6 The designation "RICC" in this work is kept just for continuity of the traditional names of the closure
 7 components. The advantage of this approach is that the result does not have to rely on any presumptions
 8 of modelling or the trustworthiness of their results. Numerical models typically need some parameters to
 9 be set up phenomenologically anyway. In fact, it is not known which mechanisms exactly can be present.
 10 The ΔK_{RICC} component introduced by Eq. (11) includes the overall effect including any possible unknown
 11 mechanisms of crack tip shielding, including crack branching or interactions of RICC with PICC or other
 12 mechanisms. The results of any modelling should be close to this value, otherwise the FCG rates would
 13 not be described well. Although the value according to Eq. (11) is only phenomenological, its
 14 significance is in establishing of the frame, in which the results of modelling should fit and it can serve
 15 for their verification. It is also the first time that the effect of RICC on FCG rate is really expressed
 16 quantitatively and it is separated from the evaluated PICC and also from the OICC effect, owing to the
 17 use of data measured in dry air.

18 In order to graphically express the newly defined constituents of ΔK , an extra line was defined in the
 19 crack growth rate diagrams presented in this article. It was plotted as the dashed blue line, as shown in the
 20 schematic diagram in Fig. 1. It represents the ΔK_{PICC} effect added to ΔK_{eff} . For every crack growth rate
 21 da/dN , the quantity $\Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K_{\text{PICC}}$ is computed to build the dashed blue line. Using the relationship (9), it
 22 can be shown that the quantity is equal to the difference between ΔK and ΔK_{RICC} , keeping in mind that the
 23 sums are defined for data measured in dry air, where OICC is assumed to be zero.

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K_{\text{PICC}} = \Delta K - \Delta K_{\text{RICC}} \quad (12)$$

25 Both sides of Eq. (12) define the borderline between the area for PICC and the area for RICC in the
 26 diagram in Fig. 1. Realizing that the difference between the data measured in humid air and the data
 27 measured in dry air is equal to the OICC component, the graphical separation of all ΔK components can
 28 be done, as depicted by the dimensions in Fig. 1. The left-hand side of Eq. (12) is used for the evaluation,
 29 since it is more straightforward to be expressed. The quantity ΔK_{PICC} according to Eq. (8) is used. Note
 30 that this quantity is not equal to fK_{max} .

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K \left(\frac{f-R^+}{1-R} \right) \quad (\text{blue dashed line horizontal coordinate}) \quad (13)$$

32

1
2 Fig. 1. Schematic division of the total crack closure effect into the individual components
3 ΔK_{PICC} , ΔK_{RICC} and ΔK_{OICC} using the crack growth rate curves for high load ratio (green
4 solid line), low load ratio in dry air (blue solid line), low load ratio in humid air (red solid
5 line) and the dashed line defined by Eq. (13). Note that for $R = 0.8$ the crack growth
6 behaviour in dry air and in humid air does not differ.
7

9 2.4 Separation of the oxide-induced crack closure effect

10 The difference between the data measured in humid air and in dry air are denoted as ΔK_{OICC} .

$$11 \quad \Delta K_{\text{OICC}} = \Delta K_{R=0.1,\text{th}}(\text{humid air}) - \Delta K_{R=0.1,\text{th}}(\text{dry air}) \quad 0 \leq R < 1 \quad (14)$$

12 Note that for negative load ratios, the values in the form of K_{max} must be considered, see also
13 Section 2.5.2.

$$14 \quad \Delta K_{\text{OICC}} = K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{humid air}) - K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{dry air}) \quad R < 0 \quad (15)$$

15 Similar to the previously established terminology, the symbol ΔK_{OICC} does not necessarily mean that it is
16 caused the oxide-induced crack closure only. It includes all effects resulting from air humidity, which
17 means that it also includes the secondary effects. If ΔK is higher at threshold or at a certain crack growth
18 rate because of OICC, other components are larger too, namely, the ΔK_{PICC} component is larger due to a
19 larger K_{max} . Therefore, the value of ΔK_{OICC} represents the combined effect of all mechanisms when the air
20 becomes humid in comparison to the case of dry air.

21 The value of $\Delta K_{\text{OICC,th}}$ represents an important parameter revealing the characteristic range, in which
22 the conventionally obtained threshold ΔK_{th} (measured in humid air) typically varies for a particular
23 material. In contrast, the remaining threshold components are not much dependent on the testing
24 conditions and are given rather by the material mechanical properties. They exhibit similar values for all
25 steels, making them much more predictable. They also represent conservative values. This makes an
26 intermediate step between using ΔK_{th} , which is the most influenced, non-conservative and unpredictable
27 value, and the effective threshold $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$, which is the lowest, most conservative and predictable value.

1 Although the effective threshold represents the true materials resistance to cracking, it is often too much
 2 conservative to be used in applications at low load ratios.

3 It is important to note that the knowledge of $\Delta K_{\text{OICC,th}}$ is essential for the development of predictive
 4 tools of ΔK_{th} under given operational conditions. A dynamic model of oxide debris growth cannot work
 5 without determination of the amount of OICC typical for the investigated material. Such a model could be
 6 used in the cases where the dry air threshold would be too much conservative, while the operational
 7 conditions would be known with certainty, especially the evolution of air humidity. Such simulation
 8 could provide as precise results as possible. Note that the dry air threshold is associated with absolute
 9 humidity and thus it is relevant for operation at low temperatures in winter, see [23]. It should also be
 10 noted that ΔK_{OICC} is the result of particular loading histories under certain experimental conditions, hence
 11 it should not be simply added to the dry air threshold with the purpose of obtaining a material parameter
 12 for humid air. One should also avoid the mistake of adding an estimated ΔK_{OICC} component to a threshold
 13 that is not completely ensured to be measured in dry air or with the elimination of OICC by another way.
 14 In such a case, the OICC component would be considered twice in the simulation, which is non-
 15 conservative.

16 **2.5 Completion of the NASGRO equation for simulations**

17 To compute RFL, the NASGRO equation should be integrated from the initial crack length to the
 18 defined final crack length. External loading is given by the number of cycles at certain SIF ranges and
 19 load ratios. Some missing quantities for the equation are presented in this section.

20 **2.5.1 The crack closure function f for all load ratios**

21 In computations of RFL, the dependence of da/dN on the load ratio R must be complete. The
 22 experimentally corrected f value from Section 2.2 serves for an accurate evaluation of the PICC effect at a
 23 selected load ratio. For other load ratios, the results of the strip-yield model can be used [33,34]. If the
 24 model is available, an option is to run simulations for various R and to obtain stabilized crack opening
 25 loads. This way has the advantage of consideration of the experimentally obtained f for particular
 26 materials, as described in the present work. A special variable in the model accounts for the material, as
 27 suggested in [31]. Another option is to take the commonly used formulae for the f parameter used in
 28 NASGRO, which also originate from strip-yield model simulations. These fitting equations are available
 29 and generally known [40] but they exhibit some deviations of f from the experimentally obtained values.

30 **2.5.2 Dependence of threshold on load ratio R**

31 The last step to complete the NASGRO equation is the dependence of the threshold on the load ratio.
 32 The dependence can be obtained experimentally or by methods established by each laboratory. In the
 33 present work, it is based on the two basic experimental values: the effective threshold $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ and the
 34 threshold expressed in terms of K_{max} obtained for the selected low load ratio ($R = 0.1$), which is $K_{\text{max,th}}$.
 35 The second value is determined using Eq. (16) from the measured threshold $\Delta K_{\text{th},R=0.1}$.

$$36 \quad K_{\text{max,th}} = \frac{\Delta K_{\text{th},R=0.1}}{1-R} \quad (R = 0.1) \quad (16)$$

37 Then, using the effective threshold $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$, typically obtained at $R = 0.8$, the transition load ratio R_t
 38 is computed as:

$$39 \quad R_t = 1 - \frac{\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}}{K_{\text{max,th}}} \quad (17)$$

The dependence of ΔK_{th} on R is then defined according to Eq. (18). It is divided into two intervals, below the transition load ratio R_t and above it. The first interval corresponds to the closure-dominated region ($R < R_t$), while in the second interval ($R_t < R < 1$) the values are presumed to be equal to the effective threshold.

$$\Delta K_{th} = \begin{cases} (1 - R)K_{max,th} & \dots \dots \dots \text{ for } R < R_t \\ \Delta K_{eff,th} & \dots \dots \dots \text{ for } R_t \leq R < 1 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

This can be used for both dry air and humid air thresholds. Although this approach is somewhat simplified, it is a straightforward one and easy to apply without major errors. In some materials, the threshold exhibits slight decrease for negative R . For $R > 1$, the whole cycle is in compression so there is no easily describable crack propagation threshold for mode I.

3 Experiments and results

3.1 Materials

The presented methodology was applied on to five investigated materials, for which fatigue crack growth rates and thresholds were measured. In relation to the focus on the role of the OICC mechanism, three two non-corroding (stainless) and three corroding (low alloyed/carbon) steels were selected. The basic mechanical properties of the experimental materials and their chemical composition are presented in Table 1 and Table 2, while their microstructures are shown in Figs. 2(a)–(e).

X20Cr13

The first investigated material is martensitic stainless steel X20Cr13. This grade combines good wear resistance and high hardness in the quenched-tempered state with sufficient corrosion resistance and good machinability. It is widely used in various industries, such as plastic molds and dies, hand tools, pumps, and various accessories in the oil industry, and many more. Its nominal chemical composition is shown in Table 1. Material used in the study was delivered in the form of forged bar, after quench-tempering heat treatment, producing a homogeneous microstructure consisting of tempered martensite, as shown in Fig. 2(a).

GX4CrNi13-4

The second examined material is the cast stainless steel GX4CrNi13-4. This steel exhibits excellent mechanical strength even at elevated temperatures, while retaining its corrosion resistance. It is usually used for highly exposed structural parts in the energy industry, as turbines and high-pressure components. Material for study was delivered in quench-tempered condition, with resulting martensitic microstructure with a minor delta ferrite content. The microstructure of steel grade B is shown in Fig. 2(b). In contrast to X20Cr13, GX4CrNi13-4 exhibits a coarser initial parent austenite microstructure due to the casting process, which could influence the crack propagation mechanism.

EA1N

The next steel considered in this study is one of the most widely used materials for railway axles fabrication designated EA1N. It is a low-carbon steel, microalloyed with small amounts of Ni, Cr, Mo and V. The EA1N steel is usually used in normalized conditions, which is the state that was examined in the present study. Normalization treatment results in the pearlitic-ferritic microstructure, as shown in

Fig. 2(c). The EA1N steel combines sufficient mechanical strength and toughness with a very good resistance to wear damage, which are properties demanded in the railway industry.

EA4T

Another prominent railway axle steel, designated EA4T, was also included in the study. Similar to EA1N, EA4T is a low-carbon microalloyed steel. It is usually operated in the quenched-tempered condition, resulting in high strength and hardness. The microstructure after quenching and tempering shown in Fig. 2(d) consists of a mixture of bainite and tempered martensite. Due to its properties, EA4T is frequently used in high-performance applications, such as the driving axles.

P265GH

The last investigated material is the non-alloy carbon steel P265GH, dedicated to the use in the energy and petrochemical industry. Due to the low carbon content, P265GH exhibits excellent weldability with a good balance of strength and plasticity. Microstructure after homogenization heat treatment consists of a mixture of ferrite and pearlite (Fig. 2(e)), resulting in high ductility. It is often used for pressurized vessels and pipes, operated at elevated temperatures.

Table 1: Designation and chemical composition of the investigated materials.

Material designation	Chemical composition obtained via glow discharge optical spectroscopy (GDOS)					
	C [wt.%]	Si [wt.%]	Mn [wt.%]	Cr [wt.%]	Ni [wt.%]	Mo [wt.%]
X20Cr13	0.19	0.41	0.52	13.73	0.68	–
GX4CrNi13-4	0.032	0.27	0.43	12.21	4.46	0.43
EA1N	0.37	0.29	0.98	0.068	0.028	0.013
EA4T	0.26	0.26	0.76	1.11	0.039	0.22
P265GH	0.17	0.30	1.18	–	–	–

Table 2: Basic mechanical properties of the investigated materials.

Material designation	Yield strength [MPa]	Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]	Young modulus E [GPa]	Elongation at break
X20Cr13	600	790	205	18 %
GX4CrNi13-4	550	760	190	15 %
EA1N	350	550	210	24 %
EA4T	610	730	204	23 %
P265GH	265	460	190	27 %

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Fig. 2. Optical microscopy images at two magnifications (left and right) of the metallography cuts showing the microstructure of the investigated materials (a) X20Cr13, (b) GX4CrNi13-4, (c) EA1N, (d) EA4T, (e) P265GH.

3.2 Measurement of fatigue crack growth rates

In this work, the crack closure effects are evaluated from the experimentally obtained fatigue crack growth rate curves. The curve measured at $R = 0.8$ is presumed to provide ΔK_{eff} data. The curves for $R = 0.1$ measured in dry and humid air serve to reveal the basic effect of load ratio and oxide debris. The fatigue crack growth rates da/dN were measured using the middle-crack tension M(T) specimens with the width $2W = 60$ mm and the thickness $B = 5$ mm for the steels X20Cr13, GX4CrNi13-4, EA1N and EA4T. In the case of the steel P265GH, the compact tension C(T) specimens with the parameter $W = 30$ mm and the thickness $B = 6$ mm were used. Geometry of the specimens is schematically depicted in Fig. 3.

A sharp notch was produced by electric discharge machining with the wire diameter of 0.25 mm. The experiments with the M(T) specimens were performed using a resonant testing machine Schenck PVQ with the force capacity of 60 kN. The experiments with the C(T) specimens were performed using a linear motor testing machine Instron electropulse 10000 with the force capacity of 10 kN. All experiments were tested at frequencies in the range from 40 to 80 Hz.

The temperature and humidity was controlled in the laboratory. The temperature was set to 23 °C and the absolute humidity was set to 10 grams of water molecules per cubic meter, which corresponds approximately to 50% of relative humidity at 23 °C. The specimens tested in humid air were exposed directly to the controlled laboratory air. The specimens tested in dry air were surrounded by a special chamber for reduction of humidity. The amount of water vapour inside the chamber was reduced by the presence of silica gel particles. The absolute humidity was kept below 2 grams of water molecules per cubic meter, which corresponds to relative humidity lower than 10% at 23 °C. The chambers were originally designed by authors, one for the M(T) specimens, see Fig. 4(a), and one for the C(T) specimens, see Fig. 4(b). The chamber for the M(T) specimens had no mechanical effect on the specimen, which was tested and reported in [13], where more details about the usage of this chamber can also be found. Due to much smaller stiffness and loading force, the chamber for the C(T) specimens had to be mechanically isolated, see the scheme in Fig. 4(b). Relative humidity inside the chamber was monitored using two sensors of the type HIH4000-003 (accuracy of $\pm 3.5\%$) and the temperature inside the chamber was measured using the temperature sensor SMT 160-30.

Fig. 3. Geometry of the M(T) specimen (left) and C(T) specimen (right) used for the experiments.

Fig. 4. Sealed chamber surrounding the specimen during silica experiments in dry air, (a) the M(T) specimen, (b) the C(T) specimen with dynamic isolation. Silica gel particles were located inside the chamber to pump out air moisture.

1 The precracks in the M(T) specimens were initiated at the notch root using the force amplitude
2 $F_a = 23$ kN at the load ratio $R = -1$, which resulted in the initial maximum SIFs in the range from 10 to
3 $14 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ depending on the notch length. Note that the whole cycle range at $R = -1$ contributes to
4 crack initiation in the notch. Therefore, relatively small maximum SIF could be used, which is good to
5 reduce the effect of overload and not to use too large loading force of the testing machine. On the other
6 hand, the C(T) specimens can be loaded only at a positive load ratio. This is why the maximum initial
7 SIFs were in the range from 15 to $16 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$. The precracks were initiated in the notch root using cyclic
8 force with the amplitude $F_a = 1.72$ kN and the load ratio $R = 0.1$.

9 During the test, the crack increments were measured optically using digital cameras fixed to
10 a travelling table equipped with the micro-position measurement system with the accuracy of 0.01 mm.
11 The crack length was measured on both specimen surfaces and the values were averaged (two crack
12 lengths for the C(T) specimen, four crack lengths for the M(T) specimen). This methodology has been
13 successfully used for a long time and provided reliable data for many experiments. The advantage of this
14 method is that the crack length is measured directly, and it is not calculated from other variables, such as
15 changes in the electrical resistivity or the mechanical stiffness.

16 After the crack initiated and reached 1 mm, the experiment started with a step-wise load shedding
17 (ΔK -decreasing) procedure to determine the crack growth threshold. The load amplitude reduction
18 corresponded to the parameter $C = -0.4 \text{ mm}^{-1}$ defined in the standard ASTM E647 [25]. After the crack
19 stopped at threshold, the force amplitude was increased and the crack was re-propagated with a gradually
20 increasing ΔK until the final fracture. The da/dN - ΔK data were processed according to the standard
21 ASTM E647 in order to exclude invalid data points (e.g. a too large difference between the lengths
22 measured on the two sides).

24 3.3 Processed crack growth rate curves and fracture surfaces

25 For each material a set of three crack growth rate curves were measured and presented in Figs. 5 – 9:
26 (i) at $R = 0.8$ in humid air – green points and solid fitting line, (ii) at $R = 0.1$ in dry air – blue points and
27 solid fitting line and (iii) at $R = 0.1$ in humid air – red points and solid fitting line. In addition, a blue
28 dashed line is plotted as a border between PICC and RICC, as explained in Section 2.3. The experimental
29 points at $da/dN = 10^{-9}$ mm/cycle were plotted for cases when no more crack growth was detected.

30 Based on observation of the fracture surfaces, several statements can be made. At $R = 0.1$ in humid
31 air, an increasingly significant oxide debris layer was formed and visible optically at the fracture surfaces
32 when approaching the crack arrest at threshold. At $R = 0.1$ in dry air, the oxide layer was significantly
33 eliminated. A full elimination of the oxide would require the air to be fully dry, the water vapour
34 completely pumped out, which was not possible with the simple technology of silica gel particles. Even
35 with the used technology, the threshold was noticeably smaller in dry air. This was the case of all
36 investigated steels, including the stainless steels, which is quite surprising and remarkable. It reveals that
37 the effect of OICC is not limited to corroding steels. Surface oxidation plays a significant role in
38 corrosion-resistant steels, perhaps due to the repeated mechanical disruption of the passivation layer.

39 The observed clean fracture surfaces at $R = 0.8$ in humid air confirmed that the enhanced oxide layer
40 was not formed and that crack closure causing repeated contact pressure is the necessary condition for the
41 formation of oxide debris.

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3 Fig. 5. (a) Experimental crack growth rates and their fitting lines for the X20Cr13 steel obtained
 4 at $R = 0.8$ in humid air (green diamonds), at $R = 0.1$ in dry air (blue circles) and at $R = 0.1$
 5 in humid air (red crosses) accompanied by the blue dashed line separating the PICC and
 6 RICC components of ΔK , as defined in Section 3.3. (b) – (d) light microscopy images of
 7 the fracture surfaces of the corresponding specimens. The investigated area of crack
 8 propagation is marked by the white vertical arrow and the crack arrest at the measured
 9 threshold is underlined by the white dotted line.

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3 Fig. 6. (a) Experimental crack growth rates and their fitting lines for the GX4CrNi13-4 steel
 4 obtained at $R = 0.8$ in humid air (green diamonds), at $R = 0.1$ in dry air (blue circles) and
 5 at $R = 0.1$ in humid air (red crosses) accompanied by the blue dashed line separating the
 6 PICC and RICC components of ΔK , as defined in Section 3.3. (b) – (d) light microscopy
 7 images of the fracture surfaces of the corresponding specimens. The investigated area of
 8 crack propagation is marked by the white vertical arrow and the crack arrest at the
 9 measured threshold is underlined by the white dotted line.

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3 Fig. 7. (a) Experimental crack growth rates and their fitting lines for the EA1N steel obtained at
 4 $R = 0.8$ in humid air (green diamonds), at $R = 0.1$ in dry air (blue circles) and at $R = 0.1$ in
 5 humid air (red crosses) accompanied by the blue dashed line separating the PICC and
 6 RICC components of ΔK , as defined in Section 3.3. (b) – (d) light microscopy images of
 7 the fracture surfaces of the corresponding specimens. The investigated area of crack
 8 propagation is marked by the white vertical arrow and the crack arrest at the measured
 9 threshold is underlined by the white dotted line.

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3 Fig. 8. (a) Experimental crack growth rates and their fitting lines for the EA4T steel obtained at
 4 $R = 0.8$ in humid air (green diamonds), at $R = 0.1$ in dry air (blue circles) and at $R = 0.1$ in
 5 humid air (red crosses) accompanied by the blue dashed line separating the PICC and
 6 RICC components of ΔK , as defined in Section 3.3. (b) – (d) light microscopy images of
 7 the fracture surfaces of the corresponding specimens. The investigated area of crack
 8 propagation is marked by the white vertical arrow and the crack arrest at the measured
 9 threshold is underlined by the white dotted line.

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3 Fig. 9. (a) Experimental crack growth rates and their fitting lines for the P265GH steel obtained
 4 at $R = 0.8$ in humid air (green diamonds), at $R = 0.1$ in dry air (blue circles) and at $R = 0.1$
 5 in humid air (red crosses) accompanied by the blue dashed line separating the PICC and
 6 RICC components of ΔK , as defined in Section 3.3. (b) – (d) light microscopy images of
 7 the fracture surfaces of the corresponding specimens. The investigated area of crack
 8 propagation is marked by the white vertical arrow and the crack arrest at the measured
 9 threshold is underlined by the white dotted line.

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3.4 Extraction of important parameters and decomposition of ΔK_{th}

As described in Sections 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4, the parameters of the fitting Eqs. (2) and (3) provide useful information about the composition of ΔK in relation to driving force and closure. Table 3 presents the obtained fitting parameters. The values then enabled determination of the crack closure parameter f according to Eq. (6) and the crack closure components for threshold loading $\Delta K_{PICC,th}$, $\Delta K_{RICC,th}$ and $\Delta K_{OICC,th}$ according to Eqs. (8), (10) and (14), respectively. The results are summarized in Table 4.

The components $\Delta K_{eff,th}$, $\Delta K_{PICC,th}$, $\Delta K_{RICC,th}$ and $\Delta K_{OICC,th}$ were graphically expressed in Fig. 10 to offer a much better overview of their significance and the corresponding resistance to fatigue crack growth. Owing to this diagram, the responsible mechanisms forming the total threshold can be clearly imagined. Although slight shifts of some of the components can be subject to discussion, such decomposition is unprecedented and offers a unique insight into the complex problem of fatigue crack growth threshold. The OICC component enables assessment of the range, in which the traditionally defined threshold may vary due to experimental conditions.

Table 3: Fitting parameters of the crack growth rate Eqs. (2) and (3) obtained based on the experimental data.

Material	C_{eff} [*]	$C_{R=0.1}$ [*]	n [*]	p [-]	$\Delta K_{eff,th}$ [MPa·m ^{0.5}]	$\Delta K_{R=0.1,th}$ (dry air) [MPa·m ^{0.5}]	$\Delta K_{R=0.1,th}$ (humid air) [MPa·m ^{0.5}]
X20Cr13	$7.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$	3.2	0.65	2.8	4.8	5.7
GX4CrNi13-4	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.4	0.75	2.7	3.6	4.5
EA1N	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.8	0.60	3.0	4.6	5.2
EA4T	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.6	0.70	2.5	4.2	6.1
P265GH	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.8	0.70	3.0	5.0	7.0

*Units of C and n correspond to da/dN values in [mm/cycle].

Table 4: Crack closure parameters calculated using Eqs. (6), (8), (11) and (14).

Material	$f =$ K_{PICC}/K_{max}	$\Delta K_{PICC,th}$ [MPa·m ^{0.5}]	$\Delta K_{RICC,th}$ [MPa·m ^{0.5}]	$\Delta K_{OICC,th}$ [MPa·m ^{0.5}]
X20Cr13	0.29	1.01	1.04	0.9
GX4CrNi13-4	0.29	0.77	0.13	0.9
EA1N	0.18	0.42	1.18	0.6
EA4T	0.19	0.44	1.26	1.9
P265GH	0.18	0.45	1.55	2.0

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3 Fig. 10. Graphical summary of the threshold ΔK_{th} decomposition with respect to the mechanisms
4 for the five investigated materials. The effective threshold $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$, the plasticity-induced
5 crack closure component $\Delta K_{\text{PICC,th}}$, the roughness-induced crack closure component
6 $\Delta K_{\text{RICC,th}}$ and the oxide-induced crack closure component $\Delta K_{\text{OICC,th}}$.

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4 Discussion

4.1 Significance of the results and general discussion

Experimental techniques of crack closure measurement, such as the back face or crack mouth opening displacement techniques are not reliable and many discussions and questions arise about the relevance of the results. While they still represent a way to obtain the values, especially under variable-amplitude loading, the presented method offers to find the crack closure parameters without any problematic measurement techniques. Moreover, the possibility of separation to individual closure components is offered.

4.1.1 PICC evaluated from crack growth rates versus numerical modelling

One of the interesting findings of the presented procedure is that the characteristic crack closure parameter f for the 5 investigated materials were obtained directly from the crack growth rates without any necessity of measurement or modelling of crack closure. These values are not affected by any problematic aspects of the crack closure theory in the sense of the direct contact determination techniques. Looking at the results in Table 4, two groups of materials with similar numbers were formed, one for the non-corroding steels ($f \approx 0.3$) and one for the corroding steels ($f \approx 0.2$). The reason can only be a subject of speculation. It is clear, though, that without the newly proposed methodology, this information about the materials would be lost and the true f values could not be compared in this way. They would be computed as ≈ 0.25 for all materials. The presented methodology not only saves time and effort by avoiding crack closure measurement but it also removes the need for finite element modelling of PICC. These numerical models are typically too complex with high demands on computational time with insufficient ability to predict. Many parameters of the simulation need to be calibrated, in which case the experimental data for the material need to be available anyway. The reliability of crack closure experimental measurement has been subject to debate for a long time with no consensus. The present study offers the advantage of overcoming this problem by means of a very simple and straightforward determination of the crack closure values. These arguments are valid for constant amplitude loading. Modelling and measurement of crack closure is still required in the case of variable amplitude loading.

4.1.2 Remarks to roughness-induced crack closure

For a long time it was too difficult, if possible, to separate the RICC component from the other closure components near threshold. It was known that the RICC plays a role but its quantification was problematic either by experimental techniques or by numerical modelling. Owing to the new strategy, it is possible to eliminate the OICC component by measurement in dry air. After evaluation of PICC, the RICC is determined simply as the remaining component of closure. This decomposition follows the conclusion of the recently published study [22] where the use of solely PICC in the analysis was not sufficient to describe completely the near-threshold behaviour. Thus the present work represents a significant step forward in the research of crack closure. As mentioned though, the real mechanism of the RICC component does not have to be the wedging effect due to the mating fracture surface mismatch. It can be a combination with crack branching or other phenomena not clarified yet. This is probably the reason why mechanistic models have not been successful in correct quantification of RICC in real materials.

4.1.3 Oxide-induced crack closure in stainless steels

An interesting result was obtained that the OICC effect in stainless steels is very comparable to the OICC effect in corroding steels. This demonstrates that the mechanism of repeated disruption of the oxidized metallic surface occurs independently of the ability of the material to create a passivation layer.

1 Fresh metal is always exposed for oxidation after high pressure with friction occurs during each loading
2 cycle. The results also lead to the idea that the wedging effect of oxide (and possibly metal) debris is not
3 the only mechanism of OICC. The oxide layer in stainless steels should not provoke volume increase in
4 the crack wake, since the Pilling-Bedworth ratio [41] is close to one, which is the reason for corrosion
5 protection. Additionally, very frequent crack branching was observed in the microscopic analysis of the
6 oxide debris layers, e.g. [9]. These branches are probably generated when the main crack front gets
7 arrested due to increased crack closure and the crack is looking for alternative paths. Crack branching is
8 also a crack tip shielding effect, diminishing the crack driving force. In the sense of the present study, this
9 effect would be included in the ΔK_{OICC} component and it could explain its presence in the corrosion
10 resistant steels.

11 **4.1.4 Significance for testing and residual fatigue life estimation**

12 In many applications, the whole loading spectrum is important for the RFL. Usually the smallest
13 amplitudes are the most frequent ones and they lie below or in the near-threshold area. If this was not the
14 case, the component would be insufficiently designed. It is a very frequent practice that the crack growth
15 rate curve is measured only in the Paris regime and the threshold area is omitted. This is perhaps due to
16 untrustworthiness of the near-threshold data due to experimental difficulties. The present study could be
17 helpful in this situation, since the proposed methodology eliminates large scatter of the threshold data due
18 to various experimental conditions.

19 The use of ΔK_{th} measured in dry air for estimation of RFL will generally lead to conservative results.
20 In the cases where a high accuracy of the numerical RFL estimates is required, the addition of the ΔK_{OICC}
21 component can be desired to simulate larger thresholds under specific experimental and operational
22 conditions. This includes the loading history effects that affect the threshold measured in humid air. Using
23 standard procedures means that in most cases the experimental measurements have different loading
24 histories than in operation, which is also true for loading frequency and specimen geometry. Therefore,
25 such artificially increased thresholds could be dangerous to be used.

26 If researchers are confident enough to simulate operational conditions, then the ΔK_{OICC} component
27 can be simulated by a dynamic cycle-by-cycle oxide debris growth model. Such a dynamic model is
28 currently under development, however, it is not the scope of the present article. The data measured in
29 humid air represent the source of information about the scatter and limits of ΔK_{OICC} , which is a necessary
30 input for particular materials into such a simulation.

31 **4.2 Comparison to other alternative threshold measurement methods**

32 Alternative methods for threshold determination were mentioned in Introduction, such as the
33 compression precrack load reduction (CPLR) technique [27,28] and the K_{max} -constant technique [29].
34 These methods provide more conservative thresholds than the standard load shedding procedure. They
35 partially get rid of the excessive closure components at threshold. This is significant especially for non-
36 ferrous metals. In the case of steels, the presented methodology of dry air measurement offers some
37 advantages. The reduction of OICC is much more pronounced, leading to the use of a fundamental
38 material-related threshold. Furthermore, the widely used experimental procedures established in
39 laboratories, such as those corresponding to the standards ASTM or ISO, can still be applied with no
40 necessity of development of new techniques. Only the dry air chamber is required. Another advantage of
41 the present approach is that it offers an insight into the responsible mechanisms and the significance of
42 individual crack closure components.

1 It should be noted that the cyclic R-curve method (e. g. [42]) also uses the compression precrack and
2 it is useful for elimination of any PICC overload effects on threshold. Unfortunately, the most convenient
3 loading histories to reduce PICC are the ones that produce the largest OICC effect. This is brought to an
4 extreme in the case of the cyclic R-curve procedure, where the repeated crack arrests result in massive
5 oxide debris layers. The dependence of the threshold on the crack length is too long, with the values
6 increasing continuously into dangerously non-conservative ranges. The corresponding crack extensions
7 are as large as 8 mm, which is impractical for RFL calculations. At such crack lengths, the fatigue life of
8 a component is practically ended. Therefore, the dependence should be either measured in dry air or it
9 should be truncated at about 2 mm crack length.

10 **4.3 Possible limitations and further questions**

11 The presented quantification of the crack closure components should not be taken as a proof that the
12 conventionally understood physical mechanisms really result in these values. As mentioned, the names of
13 the closure components were used to keep the continuity of using them in discussions, as they were
14 established in the literature. The values should be understood as the first step forward to improve the
15 closure quantification by the NASGRO approach, where only PICC is considered. The results showed
16 reasonable decomposition of the threshold value into the PICC, RICC and OICC influences. The PICC
17 value was derived from the Paris regime. The RICC value was simply defined as the rest of the applied
18 ΔK , to which no other component was assigned. The OICC influence should not be understood as
19 solely the effect of oxide debris wedging between the fracture surfaces. A part of the effect corresponds to
20 the increased PICC effect due to the larger K_{\max} value at threshold. It is also probable that more effects
21 contribute to the ΔK_{OICC} component defined in this study, since the process of crack tip shielding is more
22 complex at a microscale, e.g. due to crack branching. Although the obtained closure values are
23 phenomenological, they were expressed quantitatively for the first time and they can serve as the range in
24 which the future models should provide the values in order to match the experimental crack growth rates.
25 In relation to the complexity of the threshold topic, as summarized in the Introduction, several questions
26 should be considered to improve the validity and completeness of the discussion.

27 **4.3.1 Are the high- R data really the same in dry air and in humid air?**

28 In this work, it was presumed that air humidity does not affect the experiment at high load ratio
29 ($R = 0.7$ or $R = 0.8$). This can be supported by the fact that the effect of humidity is caused by oxide-
30 induced crack closure. If crack closure was present and oxide debris accumulated, the effective threshold
31 would divert noticeably from the expected range of $2.5 - 3.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, which is based on numerous
32 experiments as well as the theoretical estimate $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} = 0.8Eb^{0.5} = 2.6 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, where E is the Young
33 modulus and b is the magnitude of the Burgers vector [15-19]. This relationship has been established long
34 time ago and it has been widely used to obtain good estimates for various conventional metallic materials.
35 Additionally, the data in dry air were measured for the EA4T steel at $R = 0.8$, revealing no dependence of
36 the threshold on humidity [13]. Clean fracture surfaces of the specimens tested at $R = 0.8$ in humid air,
37 see Figs. 5–9 (b), are also a sign of no OICC influence.

38 **4.3.2 Are the high- R data really equal to ΔK_{eff} ?**

39 As mentioned above, the effective threshold $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ is a well predictable parameter and the results are
40 in agreement with the common value for all steels. Therefore, the presented separation of crack closure at
41 threshold is valid. It should be noted that the experimental values of $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ depend on the crack growth
42 rate defining the threshold. As pointed out in [8], the crack growth rate curve measured at high R
43 continues smoothly down below 10^{-7} mm/cycle for decreasing ΔK , making a difference between the
44 requirement by the standard ASTM E647 [25], which is 10^{-7} mm/cycle and the standard ISO 12108 [37],

1 which is 10^{-8} mm/cycle. The variation of $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ according to these two standards was approx. from 2.2 to
2 $2.8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for the S690QL steel, which was verified using several different measurement techniques.
3 For cases with crack closure, it is suggested that the larger values are used, since at low load ratios (such
4 as $R = 0.1$) the curve turns down sharply to the threshold at about 10^{-7} mm/cycle due to the increasing
5 RICC and OICC effects. Thus the crack becomes arrested even when ΔK is no longer decreased. For the
6 purpose of the crack closure analysis, data at equal da/dN were considered. Therefore, it is not necessary
7 to define $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ for very low crack growth rates. This enables saving of the testing time considerably.

8 The remaining question is about the rest of the FCG rate curve. At high FCG rates, the K_{max} at $R = 0.8$
9 could already fall beyond the small-scale yielding condition. Additionally, effects such as residual stress,
10 cyclic creep or partial monotonic ductile/brittle fracture could play a role. This area of high mean stress
11 effects has limited understanding and availability of data and it should be further investigated.
12 Nevertheless, the presented FCG rate curves for $R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.8$ still have equal slopes in the log-log
13 scale, indicating that the measured range was maintained in the area of validity of ΔK . This supports the
14 validity of the method for extracting the crack closure parameter f from these measured curves.

15 **4.3.3 Can the PICC values be simply taken from the Paris regime and applied to the** 16 **near-threshold regime?**

17 The results of discrete dislocation dynamics of the PICC effect [43,44] revealed very similar values to
18 those obtained by continuum mechanics, i.e. $K_{\text{cl}} / K_{\text{max}} \approx 0.2$ for $R = 0$ in plane strain. Despite the near-
19 threshold regime implies anisotropy at the micro-scale and the effects of dislocation motion and storage
20 that cannot be reproduced by continuum mechanics, it seems that the predicted closure effect by these two
21 approaches do not differ too much. This is perhaps due to the averaging effect of contributions of all
22 grains along the crack front. Consequently, the presumption of equality of the PICC values in the Paris
23 regime (continuum mechanics dominance) and in the near-threshold regime (discrete dislocations
24 dominance) should not cause any noticeable errors. It can again be noted that the same practice is done in
25 the NASGRO method, so this is no new simplification brought by the presented methodology.

26 **4.3.4 What if testing in dry air is not available?**

27 It should be emphasized that thresholds obtained experimentally in humid air are affected and mostly
28 non-conservative for steels. They occur somewhere within a relatively large scatter that is unknown to the
29 experimenter if only one measurement is performed. Therefore, all parameters of the test should be
30 recorded rigorously, especially air humidity. Installation of the sealed chamber with silica gel balls is the
31 best option to obtain the dry air threshold. It can be easily mounted to the experimental setup.
32 Nevertheless, if this procedure cannot be realized, air humidity should at least be controlled at constant
33 level in order to make the experimental campaign meaningful.

34 The dry air threshold can also be estimated based on the results of this work. The best estimate for
35 conventional steels is suggested as follows: $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} = 2.7 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, $f = 0.25$ ($R = 0.1$, plane strain) and
36 ΔK_{RICC} as $1.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for conventional microstructures, $2.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for coarse grain structures (as
37 a rough estimate) and $0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for ultra-fine microstructures, see [45]. It is presumed that the load ratio
38 is low enough for the RICC component to be active. For higher load ratios, the ΔK_{RICC} component may be
39 meaningless. Qualitative significance of RICC based on the microstructure can also be assessed using the
40 size ratio defined in [44], which is the ratio of the mean grain size and the representative size of the crack
41 tip plastic zone. Using the mentioned values and Eq. (19), which is based on Eq. (9), the unknown ΔK can
42 be derived. Substituting ΔK_{PICC} from Eq. (8) will result in the term in Eq. (20). Alternatively, the
43 difference $\Delta K - \Delta K_{\text{PICC}}$ can be imagined as an "effective ΔK " in the sense of the NASGRO formula, see
44 Eq. (1).

1
$$\Delta K - \Delta K_{\text{PICC}} = \Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K_{\text{RICC}} \quad (19)$$

2
$$\Delta K \left(\frac{1-f}{1-R} \right) = \Delta K_{\text{eff}} + \Delta K_{\text{RICC}} \quad (20)$$

3 For threshold loading and considering $R = 0.1$, the estimated value is:

4
$$\Delta K_{\text{th,dry}} = \frac{\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} + \Delta K_{\text{RICC,th}}}{\frac{1-f}{1-R}} = 4.4 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}. \quad (21)$$

5 In this way, the OICC component present in conventional tests can be approximated as the difference
6 between the experimental humid air threshold and the value given by Eq. (21). This can also provide the
7 range of possible variation of the threshold due to experimental conditions. Similar estimates to those
8 made for steels could also be done for other metals using the theoretical formula for $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$. The results,
9 however, would require to be verified experimentally, which is out of the scope of the present work. The
10 RICC component is the most difficult one to predict or numerically model. Measurement in dry air is a
11 feasible way of its quantitative determination.

12 For other load ratios, Eqs. (16) to (18) in Section 2.5.2 can be used. A demonstrative example of how
13 the equations can be used is given for the most commonly used negative load ratio $R = -1$.

14
$$K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{dry}) = \frac{\Delta K_{\text{th},R=0.1}(\text{dry})}{1-0.1} = 4.9 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5} \quad (22)$$

15
$$\Delta K_{\text{th}}(\text{dry}) = (1 - R) \cdot K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{dry}) = 9.8 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5} \quad (R = -1). \quad (23)$$

16 It should be noted that for negative R the addition of the ΔK_{OICC} component should be done using the
17 $K_{\text{max,th}}$ value. Considering an example of ΔK_{OICC} being equal to $1.5 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}$ and the result of Eq. (22),
18 the humid air threshold will be obtained as follows:

19
$$K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{humid}) = K_{\text{max,th}}(\text{dry}) + \Delta K_{\text{OICC}} = 6.4 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}, \quad (24)$$

20
$$\Delta K_{\text{th}}(\text{humid}) = (1 - R)K_{\text{max,th}} = 12.8 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5} \quad (R = -1). \quad (25)$$

21 The OICC component can also be modelled, however this would be preferred for loading history
22 effects and variable-amplitude loading, similarly to the modelling of PICC. The load shedding test
23 conducted in humid air is also an example of a process influenced by loading history. A dynamic model
24 of oxide debris growth for particular testing conditions could reproduce the variation of thresholds
25 measured in humid air. It could also establish a relationship to determine ΔK_{OICC} that should be used in
26 Eq. (24) in order to make the threshold prediction complete, which is prospective as the subject of future
27 studies.

28

5 Conclusions

The presented methodology enables a straightforward quantitative separation of the total crack closure effect into the three main components defined as follows: (i) the load ratio effect observed in the Paris regime (traditionally attributed to plasticity-induced crack closure), (ii) the additional component active in the near-threshold regime (traditionally attributed to roughness-induced crack closure) and (iii) the effect of air humidity (traditionally designated as oxide-induced crack closure). The first two components are related predominantly to material properties, while the third component depends mainly on testing conditions.

Based on the results for five steel grades, the following can be concluded:

- The threshold ΔK_{th} measured in dry air (typically between $4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ and $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ at $R = 0.1$) **reflects the properties of material**, which consists of the well-predictable effective threshold $\Delta K_{eff,th}$ ($2.5\text{--}3.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$), the plasticity component ΔK_{PICC} ($0.4\text{--}1.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$) and the remaining component presumably depending on microstructure ΔK_{RICC} ($0.1\text{--}1.6 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$).
- In humid air, the measured ΔK_{th} includes an additional component designated ΔK_{OICC} ($0.6\text{--}2.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$), which **reflects the experimental influencing conditions**, such as loading frequency, loading history and air humidity. This component is the largest source of scatter and it limits the reproducibility of ΔK_{th} obtained by different laboratories in humid air in steels (typically between $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ and $8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ at $R = 0.1$). Unexpectedly, the effect of air humidity in stainless steels was as significant as in corroding steels.
- The threshold ΔK_{th} measured by load shedding using conventional testing conditions (relative air humidity above 30% at room temperature, loading frequency above 30 Hz) can be dangerous to apply if the operational loading is applied at lower frequencies or at winter time temperatures, where the absolute air humidity is much lower. These problems can be overcome by using the presented sealed chamber with silica gel mounted to the specimens, allowing the continuation of the common practice of testing using load shedding and high frequencies.

It is recommended that the threshold ΔK_{th} is measured in dry air when using it as a material parameter for conservative residual fatigue life estimation of engineering components. The new approach represents a progress in understanding of the threshold as a phenomenon, one of the most important and complex topics in metal fatigue.

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Data availability

The datasets for the current study are available at the ZENODO repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17674953>

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomáš Vojtek: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing - original draft; **Pavel Pokorný:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing - review & editing; **Radek Kubíček:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing - review & editing; **Michal Jambor:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing - review & editing; **Pavel Hutař:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing - review & editing.

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